

The Political and Ideological Structure of the Israel and Its Impact on the Security Arrangements in the Middle East with Emphasis on Iran

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Abstract

The main purpose of this study is to identify Israeli security threats (especially military threats arising from nuclear weapons programs), to investigate the impact of these threats on the regional security environment in the Middle East, and to provide solutions to deal with them. Research questions include:

- 1. What is the strategic vision and principles of Israel's national security policies?*
- 2. What are the most important security threats to Israel for the Middle East, especially the Islamic Republic of Iran?*
- 3. What policies should the countries of the region consider in dealing with these threats in their defense policy?*

The political structure of the Zionist regime is influenced by the ideological foundations of Judaism, and the teachings of the Talmud have had a great influence on the political and military actions of that regime. Overall conclusion is that while Israel's security policies pose a threat to the Middle East, for a myriad of reasons, including the growing economic vulnerability by militarism, foreign dependence on major superregional powers, especially the United States, and internal political-social-economic conflicts. Increasing the political role and armed activities of terrorist groups, the weakening and eventual overthrow of the unpopular and authoritarian Western governments in the Middle East, the Netanyahu administration will not achieve its strategic goals. The research method of this article is qualitative and the type of information gathering is documentary, desk (library) form and the use of reputable scientific sites.

Keyword: Political Structure, Ideology, Israel, Middle East, Iran

1- Introduction and problem statement

After the victory of the Islamic Revolution, Iran changed from an ally of the West to an independent country with an ideology rooted in Islam. This caused the Islamic Republic of Iran to recognize the real threats and confront the ideology of Zionism and the occupying regime.

With the rise of the Likud, a Jewish extremist party, the current structure of the Israeli regime in the political arena, led by its prime minister (Benjamin Netanyahu, a staunch opponent of Iran's pursuit of a nuclear weapon) considers Iran a major threat to the existence and security of Israel. Israel should be considered one of the most ideological countries in the world. The issue of Israeli racism is also inspired by the ideology of the Jewish people. Ideology is so intertwined in Israel's political structure that it renders it unconstitutional. Israel has no constitution and operates a set of laws that are superior to public law, called the constitution instead of the constitution. The first law of Israel is the Torah. (Reza Saadat, Page 216: 2012)

Ideologically, the Israeli authorities, referring to parts of the jurisprudential interpretation of the Torah (Talmud), believe that: "If someone comes to kill you, stand up and kill him!" Based on this, they have committed many hostile acts, including the assassination of Iraqi and Iranian nuclear scientists, as well as the assassination of Hamas leaders at the behest of Netanyahu in the Middle East. Israel considers itself the superior nation that will rule the world. According to these interpretations, if in terms of political structure, another dominant party rules over Israel that does not have extremist nationalist ideas, it is still because of the ideology of Israeli supremacy and the usurpation of Muslim lands in Palestine by this regime which is in conflict with the ideology and political structure of Iran , Iraq , the axis of resistance and other Muslim countries, but now Israel, relying on the tradition of alliance with the periphery, by establishing peace and

normalization of relations with Muslim countries, including the UAE and Bahrain, and its presence in the Caucasus region and trying equations disrupt the Middle East in order to challenge regional powers such as Iran, Russia and Turkey. These three dimensions will naturally react to any new power in the region and these reactions will cause tension and insecurity in the region, especially in Iran. (Pahlavani, 201: 1999)

The political structure of world governments is generally divided into two main ways:

1. Monarchical and authoritarian regimes (Britain and Saudi Arabia)
- 2- Democratic systems (Iran, USA, Afghanistan, etc.)

Democratic governments also govern in two main ways:

- 1- Parliamentary
- 2- Presidential

Presidential; Like Iran, where the first person in power is the president and resolves the country's problems by forming a cabinet (council of ministers). In the parliamentary system, parties play a major role in determining the first person of the country. The majority in the parliament nominates the first person of the country, who is the prime minister, who also is introduced by the president with a ceremonial position. The Israeli Zionist regime also uses the parliamentary method to govern, in which the prime minister has *carte blanche* to implement the victorious party menus (Alexandre, 48: 1987).

2- Theoretical foundations Constructivism

Efforts to explain and understand the foreign behavior of governments is one of the most important issues for international relations thinkers, and in this regard, extensive and diverse efforts have been made. Initially, this theoretical activity was essentially within the framework of general theories of international politics. But gradually, since the 1950s, another approach has emerged that focuses specifically on the study of government foreign policy. The first method has been criticized for its bigotry and disregard for what was going on within countries, but in any case the set of intellectual efforts made in international relations at various levels has led to theories based on their relation to the world to explanatory theory and they are divisible constructs that in explanatory theories fall into the objective branch of behaviorism and critical theory, but fall into the subjective branch of "constructivism."

Constructivism is an approach that has been discussed more in sociology than international relations. Since the late 1980s and early 1990s, constructivism became one of the main theories of international relations. From the constructivist point, the society of a world is not a definite world, it means there is nothing definite that its rules be discovered by scientific research and explained by scientific theory. Rather, it is an intersubjective realm, it means what makes sense to people is that build them, live in it, or understand it. They agree with the transcendentalist who believes that there is no such thing as truth and with the positivist who says that we collect dependencies and consciousness in the world.

"Went" sees government as a useful myth or metaphor, but something that is "really" something else. The state is by no means an actor, but merely a "social construct. (Waltz, 1919, 125) Of course, the meaning of this understanding often depends on whether or not other actors represent the actor in the same way. Identity in this range has a mental or system-based feature (ibid, 146).

In general, the intellectual axes in the school of constructivism can be expressed as follows:

First, actors and structures in international relations are interrelated. In fact, Went's discussion revolves around the two axes of structure - agent and scientific realism, so when discussing world politics, both structural and agent approaches must be considered. Second, the effects of this are interpreted as an imaginary community in international relations. Third, identities and interests are essential for ability levels to be able to predict history and maintain order. Over the last decade, constructivism has emerged as a school that has emerged as the main challenger of rationalism in international relations. Constructivists reject the basic premise of rationalist theory, rejecting the notion that actors pursue their set priorities over inferential logic. From the constructivists' point of view, norms shape the identity and priorities of actors and define collective goals (Fallahi, 80, 184). Transnational constructivism emphasizes the influence of norms that are widely accepted by the international

community or its subsets. Commonly used. Social constructivism emphasizes the importance of user norms in the internal society. Constructivism emphasizes the principle that foreign policy actors adhere to international or social norms, thus refuting this claim in a way that realizes that a country's foreign policy behavior changes in proportion to its increase or decrease in power. . According to this school, the power of a norm, i.e. the degree of influence on external behavior, depends on two factors: 1. Similarity, i.e. how many actors in a social system predict a common value of behavior, so the binding power of a norm depends on the degree of power. It is used by units within a social system and jointly. 2. Explicit, that is, how accurately a norm can distinguish appropriate and appropriate behavior from inappropriate and disproportionate behavior. (Rosina, 1964, 324-329).

3- The hostile actions of the Zionist regime include:

1. Assassination of 7 Iranian nuclear scientists: The assassination of Iranian nuclear figures is a series of targeted assassinations against Iranian nuclear scientists during the years 2009 to 2011. During this operation, Majid Shahriari, Mostafa Ahmadi Roshan, Massoud Ali Mohammadi, Dariush Rezainjad and Reza Qashqaei Fard were martyred, but Fereydoun Abbasi Davani survived the assassination attempt. Some of their companions were also killed or injured. In 2020, Mohsen Fakhrizadeh was assassinated in a similar attack and died. (Mottaghi, 2003: 92)

2. Assassination of a large number of Iraqi nuclear scientists and destruction of the Osirak nuclear facility in Iraq: Iraq bought the Osirak reactor nucleus from France. The reactor was originally scheduled to be shipped to Iraq in April 1979, but shortly before they were transported, an explosion occurred in a warehouse where the reactor was delayed for six months. (Anwar Alivand, 121: 1999)

After a while, the employees of the company that supplies parts to Iraq for the reactor received threatening letters from a mysterious group. Several bombs exploded in the offices of a company in Italy, as well as in the house of the company's director. Over the next few months, two other Iraqi scientists were poisoned and killed. It is very unlikely that these incidents were accidental, and many experts believe that Mossad was behind all these incidents, although it has never claimed responsibility for them. (Khosravi, 188: 2000)

Of course, this is not the first time that Israel has carried out sabotage and assassination. In the late 1950s, Egypt launched a ballistic missile program with the help of German scientists. In July 1962, President Jamal Abdel Nasser conducted two missile tests during a military parade, saying he could target targets such as "southern Beirut." Mossad reacted swiftly to "Operation Damocles," a campaign of intimidation targeting German scientists. (Entekhab Site, November 28, 2020)

3. Assassination of Hamas leaders, including Sheikh Ahmed Yassin and Abdul Aziz Rantisi: Assassination of Hamas leader Sheikh Ahmed Yassin by Israeli forces, AFP quoted Israeli radio as saying: "Israeli Prime Minister Ariel Sharon personally assassinated Sheikh Ahmed Yassin supervised. After Sheikh Ahmad Yassin, the leadership of Hamas was handed over to Rantisi within the movement. Rantisi, who led Hamas just 26 days after Sheikh Ahmad Yassin, was assassinated on Saturday, April 17, 2004, in the Gaza Strip by the Israeli Intelligence and Internal Security Agency (Shabak) in collaboration with the Israeli Air Force. (, 196James: 58)

4- Bioterrorist action against Khalid Mashal, one of the leaders of Hamas: Khalid Mashal is one of the founders of the Hamas Islamic Resistance Movement. He has been a member of the Hamas political bureau since its inception and was elected head of the bureau in 1996. On September 25, 1997, he was targeted by the Mossad terrorist operation in the Jordanian capital, which failed following the pursuit and arrest of Mossad agents by Khalid Mashal's bodyguard.

5. Espionage from various countries, including its allies, especially the United States: An Israeli spy named Jonathan Pollard, who was imprisoned in the United States for 30 years for spying for Israel, was released on Friday, November 20, and on Wednesday, January 10. The moon arrived in Israel with his wife, and Israeli

Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu greeted him at Tel Aviv International Airport and granted him and his wife an Israeli citizenship card. (Rah Peik, 255: 1999)

3. History of Israeli ideology:

The Jewish Bible is called the Torah. The Torah is the Arabic word for "Torah" in Hebrew, which means education and guidance. This book is the name of the first five books of the Old Testament or "Asfar Khamseh". The word Torah sometimes refers to the entire Old Testament. According to the Jews, God communicated these teachings to the children of Israel in five books (Safar) through Moses, the Word of God, at Mount Sinai. Christians refer to the Torah as the "Old Testament."

Asfar Khamseh or Torah, including five books as follows:

1- Journey of Genesis. Includes the story of the creation of the world, the story of Adam and Eve, Noah, Abraham, Lot, Ishmael, Isaac, Jacob (Israel) and his descendants, which ends with the death of Joseph.

2- Exit trip. The story of the slavery of the children of Israel in Egypt, the birth and prophecy of Moses (PBUH), the departure of the children of Israel from Egypt and their wandering in the desert. There are Ten Commandments in this book.

3- The journey of the Levites. It includes religious rules, worship rites, holy times and festivals.

4- Travel numbers. It includes the journey of the children of Israel in the wilderness and the events between Egypt and the Promised Land.

5- Deuteronomy. Repeating the laws and commands of the previous journeys from the language of Prophet Moses (PBUH) addressed to the children of Israel and appointing Joshua as the leader of the children of Israel and finally the death of Moses (PBUH).

The Holy Qur'an, while acknowledging the books of Moses and Jesus (PBUH) and emphasizing the heavenly origin of these books, states that some Jewish and Christian elders have distorted the Torah and the Bible and changed the heavenly books. This is stated in verse 75 of Surah Al-Baqarah: (A group of Jews hear the word of God and distort it). Also in verse 46 of Nisa, 13 of Ma'idah and 43 of Al-Imran.

Talmud

The Talmud is the name of a book on the jurisprudential interpretation of the Torah. In fact, the Talmud is the Judaism of the Jewish people, which is similar to Islamic jurisprudence and principles. Some call the Talmud an oral Torah. Every Jew belongs to one of the following two schools of thought:

Either he has a Talmudic view of Judaism or he views religion from a (mystical) perspective. The first is outward-looking and the second is inward-looking. The mystical view (Qabala'i) and the reading of the mystical book (Zohar) are not very popular among the Jews of Iran or are few and often suffice to write Shamut (combining Hebrew letters to compose amulets, blessings and curses and to influence others).

Sephardic Jews (Sephardi)

Spanish Jews who follow the Babylonian Maoist Jews are called Sephardim, belonging to the Babylonian civilization. More recently, Spain and Jewish Portugal have been referred to as Sephardic. Eastern and traditional Judaism are also called Sephardic.

Ashkenazi Jews

German-speaking Jews who are followers of Palestinian Maoist Jews are called Ashkenazis, who belong to the state of Israel. Today, Jews in Western Europe and the United States are referred to as Ashkenazi. Also called Western and modern Judaism, Ashkenazi.

Just as the Jews of the Arab world call themselves Sephardic, the Jews of Eastern Europe also prefer to call themselves Ashkenazi. Although there is no historical evidence to suggest that Jews migrated from West

Germany to the East Continent, the fact that Jews in Poland And Lithuania and Russia spoke Yiddish, as if to prove that the Jews of Eastern Europe were originally Germanic Jews - Ashkenazi Jews. (Shlomo Sand, 380: 4th of 2019 (1st, 2018))

Mizrahi Jews

Mizrahi Jews refer to Jews in the Middle East, Central Asia, and the Caucasus. The Jews of Iran, Iraq, Syria, Afghanistan, Bukhara, Kurdish and Georgian and etc are among these Jews.

4. The word Israel and its use

This people is sometimes called Jews and sometimes Hebrews. In the Qur'an, the word Israel is mentioned twice, forty times the word of the children of Israel, and once the children of Israel are mentioned, and Jews and Jews are repeated nine times in the Qur'an.

The children of Israel are also referred to by the word "tribes." For the first time, the word Israel is recorded in the Old Testament (Torah): (From now on, your name will not be called Jacob, but Israel. Because you fought with God and man and won)

5. Ancient Jewish states

The first government of the Israelites or Hebrews was founded by Saul (Talut) around 1029 BC in Canaan (Palestine).

The second Jewish state was established by the prophet David after the reign of Talut. The Jews do not consider David a prophet and refer to him as a king.

The third Jewish state was also established by Solomon the Prophet (son of David). He founded the Temple of Solomon, which was now demolished and replaced by Al-Aqsa Mosque.

Jewish mysticism: Mysticism is the confluence of two seas. The sea of theology and the art of art. Mysticism is a tasteful and heartfelt interpretation of religion as opposed to jurisprudence which is a rational interpretation of religion. Some religions are more mystical and have the capacity for mysticism: Christianity and Shiism have strong mystical tendencies; In contrast, Hanbali Judaism and mysticism escape. It should be noted that what is called mysticism in Iran and Islam has structural and content differences with Jewish mysticism. But in both, the mystery and secrecy of things are similar. Below are some important currents of Jewish mysticism. (Jafari, 85: 2004)

Mystical religion of Kabbalah (kabalah)

The peak of Jewish mysticism dates back to the 12th and 13th centuries AD (5 and 6 AH) in Islamic Spain with the city of Catalonia as its center.

The most important Jewish mystical school is called Kabbalah or Kabbalah. This school and secret and heartfelt interpretation of the Bible was narrated orally by Prophet Ibrahim (AS) and was included in the book in the Middle Ages (around the 7th century AD) and flourished in the 18th century.

The peak of the Qabalah School is in the 12th and 13th centuries, when the most important Qabalah texts, including the book "Zohar", were written in this period, and the other was the book "Khalqat", which was written in the 6th century. (Garshom Shulm, 2006: 15)

Zohar is the most famous and influential book on the heritage of Qabalah and Jewish mysticism. In Hebrew, zuhr means revelation, which in the mystical sense means divine revelation, which is full of glory and beauty, and its English meaning is Splendor. This book was written in 1275 by a person named Musa de Leon. Now this book is published in 2400 pages and 5 volumes. (Ibid, 2006: 219)

Qabalah is a school of taste and theosophy (Enlightenment Wisdom). This ritual is a reminder that has been instilled by men and for men. In the long history of Jewish mysticism, there is no sign of female influence.

In the Qabalah School, the emphasis on letters and their numerical value is so great that it even goes to extremes, leading to magic and approaching the border of superstition. Astronomy and astrology and the influence of planets also play a role in it.

The techniques of Gematria, Notarikon, and Temurah are for calculating the numerical values of Hebrew letters and words and examining their relationship to other letters and words, which is a tribal method for discovering the mysteries of the universe and divine mysticism.

Elders of Qabalah:

Ibrahim Abu al-Afiya is one of the most famous tribal elders who has many mystical written works. He was born in 1240 in Zaragoza, Spain. His prophetic teachings later found many enemies of Judaism and he was rejected by the Jews. (Garshom Shulm, 2006: 190) He considered the science of combining letters as a method for meditation. Therefore, the inference of magic from his mystical method is completely correct. With the magic of letters, he has summoned the great powers of the divine names.

Isaac Luria, Ashkenazi, developed the Qabalah religion in Palestine in the mid-16th century. In a way, after that, the qibla religion is known as Luria tribes. After Ishaq Luria, a man named Shabbat Sevi, born in Izmir, Turkey, and Nathan Gaza (Gaza) in 1625, founded a new tribal movement. In 1648, Shabtai revived the mystical school of Qabalah by claiming to be the Messiah in Gaza, but was accused of apostasy by Jewish scholars. He converted to Islam for fear of his life by referring to the court of the Ottoman sultan.

Merkabah mystical rite

Before the advent of Qabalah mysticism, early Jewish mysticism was the mysticism of the Throne or Merkaba. Qabalah religion gradually replaced Mercaba.

Merkaba means compound or throne. This period is also called the Gnostic or Hermetic period. Gnosticism emphasizes numbers and their effect.

The two books "Akhal Hekhalut" and "Asghar Hekhalut" are related to this mystical period. The physiognomy and palmistry in Khakhalut mysticism became a secret subject among mystical shaykhs, and the mysticism of Merkabai degenerated into magic and magical matters. (Garshom Shulm, 2006: 98)

Thus, in addition to reading and teaching the Talmud, a Jew had to become aware of the mysteries of the Divine Throne, the Mercabai religion, or he would not be perfect. Therefore, reading Akhal Hekhalut and the book of Enoch was strongly recommended in Judaism. (Shalmo Zand, 155: 2009)

The combination of drunkenness and magic with magic and mystery was one of the characteristics of Merkabai mysticism.

The mystical movement of Hasidism

Jewish mysticism, with its stream of Hasidism, referred to a group of Jews who rose to the heights against Hellenistic tendencies. (Garshom Shulm, 18: 2006)

As tribalism ended in Spain in the 13th century, the Hasidic movement in Germany gradually prevailed.

Hasid means piety. The founder of Hasidism, the famous saint, is "Israel Baal Shem" which appeared in the 16th century AD (Garshom Shalom, 2006: 399) Hasidic faith also seeks a reason and sign for the numerical number of words in the Torah. This kind of value view of letters and numbers also exists in Islam and has been used as the science of numbers or Jeffrey by the sect of letters. The relation of this science to Ibn Arabi has been enumerated. One of the characteristics of Hasidism is honoring marriage and the sexual aspect of life, and unlike some mystical religions, it does not command sexual abstinence and avoidance of marital affairs. In jealousy, there is the divine solution and the incarnation and image of God in the body of creatures. But in Spanish tribalism, God is incomprehensible and there is no solution for God. In Hasidic mysticism, the word and the voice are conceivable for God, just as he considers the visibility of the Holy Spirit possible. Hesidism, in addition to Germany, which was the cradle of this theology, also spread in the Netherlands and Ukraine and found supporters. (Garshom, 69: 2019)

6. Geographical location of Israel:

Israel is the official name of the state of Israel. This regime is located in West Asia, on the southeastern coast of the Mediterranean Sea and the northern coast of the Red Sea. Israel is bordered by Lebanon to the north, Syria to the northeast, Jordan to the east, the West Bank and Gaza Strip to the east and west, and Egypt to the southeast. Although it has a relatively small area, it has a variety of geographical features. The economic and scientific center of Israel is Tel Aviv, while its center of government is in Jerusalem, the city that Israel considers its capital. Jerusalem is recognized as the capital of this country by most countries, but several other countries do not recognize it. With the formation of the Zionist political movement in 1897 and the Balfour Declaration of 1917, the League of Nations, at the end of World War I and after the fall The Ottoman Empire granted custody of Palestine to Britain, with the aim of establishing "favorable political, economic, and security backgrounds for the establishment of the Jewish National House, as well as for the protection of civil and religious rights of all inhabitants of the land." "Palestine, regardless of race or religion." (Saadat, 161: 1999)

6-1-Current Israel

The First World Congress of Zionism in Bali, Switzerland, was held in 1897 to discuss the formation of a Jewish state in Palestine, Uganda, and Cyprus, and was chosen for this sinister purpose by Theodore Herzl, the Palestinian Territory (formerly the Ottoman Empire). In fact, Herzl should be called the founder of Zionism and the current state of Israel. Herzl was a Polish Jew.

In the late 19th century, a wave of anti-Semitism broke out in Europe that led to a confrontational political movement called Zionism. In November 1917, British Foreign Secretary Arthur Balfour wrote a letter to a British Zionist who promised the Balfour Declaration, and in fact the cornerstone of Israel. In this letter, Balfour asked the British Zionists to be patient and cooperate with Britain in establishing a Jewish state in Palestine, which, of course, came true 30 years later.

After World War I and the signing of the Sykes-Picot Treaty, the regions of Syria and Palestine seceded from the Ottoman Empire and came under British tutelage. At this time, with the Balfour Declaration, the wave of Jewish emigration to Palestine increased, leading to tensions between Arabs and Jews. Subsequently, in 1948, the state of Israel was officially declared, and British rule over Palestine and Syria ended. The United States and the Soviet Union were the first countries to recognize Israel. (Went.1987.132)

The structure of Israel's political system is parliamentary. Zionism emphasizes the multiplicity of parties in order to restore its illegitimate and democratic image of the regime. The Israeli parliament is called the Knesset. The parties are vying for Knesset seats, and the party that wins the majority of seats will form the government. In the last elections held in March 2020, none of the political currents succeeded in doing so, so the current government (from the Labor Party led by Netanyahu) is running the country as an interim government. The Knesset has 120 seats. Muslim and anti-Zionist parties are also represented in the Knesset. Thirteen seats in the current Knesset are occupied by Islamist parties. Below are examples of the many well-known parties in the Israeli parliament.

Ideology	Leader	Name of the party
Right wing	Benjamin Netanyahu	Likud
Social Democratic	Isaac Herzog	Israeli Labor Party
Social Democratic	Tzipi Livni	Hatoona
Moderate	Moshe Calhoun	Coolanu
Modern-right orthodox religious orthodoxy	Naftali Bennett	Jewish house
Right wing	Guido Liebermann	Israel our home
Moderate	Ehud Olmert	Kadima (qadime)
Socialist-Arab interests	Ayman odeh	Headsh

Islamist-Arab interests	Massoud Ghanim	List of United Arab Emirates
Arab interests - anti-Zionism	Jamal zahalka	Balad party
Arab-secular interests	Ibrahim Sarsour	Ta'al

The first Prime Minister of Israel was David Ben-Gurion, and during his time, the first war between the Arabs (Egypt, Syria, Jordan, and Iraq) against Israel took place in 1949. Between 1949 and 1972, Palestinian groups carried out numerous acts of persecution against Israel to retake their territory. The culmination of these attacks was the killing of members of the Israeli sports team at the 1972 Munich Olympics.

7. Politics in Israel:

Politics in Israel is dominated by Zionist parties. They are traditionally housed in three camps, the first two being the largest; there are workers' Zionism, revisionist Zionism, and religious Zionism, as well as several non-Zionist Orthodox religious parties, non-Zionist leftist groups, as well as non-Zionist (Israeli Arab citizens) and anti-Zionist parties in Israel. The type of government in Israel is a parliamentary republic. It has a parliamentary system and public suffrage. In this country, the head of state and the Knesset (Israeli parliament) act as the legislative branch.

The Knesset Constitution, paragraph 7a, 1985, stipulates that a list of candidates will not run in the Knesset elections if its explicit or implicit aims or actions include: (1) denying the existence of the state of Israel as a Jewish state; (2) denying the democratic character of the state; (3) incitement to racism (Shlomo Sand, 389: Fourth of 2019 (1st, 2018))

8. The political system of Israel:

In Israel, parties are the main actors in the political arena, they are the way of life of political and social orientations in Israel. The main parties in Israel have been formed for many years before the formation of the government, they have been divided into coalitions and divisions many times, and the coalitions and divisions continue to this day.

The Declaration of the Establishment of the State of Israel in 1948 states that; The state of Israel ... will promote the development of the country for the benefit of all its inhabitants; the state will be based on freedom, justice and peace as the prophets of Israel intended; Regardless of religion, race or gender, the government will guarantee freedom of religion, belief, language, education and culture. (Shlomo Sand, 2019: 389)

9. Key parties in Israel:

*Labor Party: In 1930, the Mapai Party was formed by merging the two old labor parties, and in the same decade became the dominant party in the country's political arena. In 1965, Mapai formed the Labor Party in alliance with the Rafi Party. Later, the Labor Party was the ruling party of Israel from 1948 to 1977, and prominent figures such as David Ben-Gurion, Shimon Peres, and Isaac Robin were members of the party. Nationalist affiliations in the Labor Party are not strong, it advocates the separation of religion from politics and the secular party.

*Likud Party: One of the extremist nationalist parties in Israel, formerly known as Horot (Freedom) and founded in Russia from 1920 to 1930.

Initially, the party advocated the formation of a government on both sides of the Jordan River, and its views gradually changed, and today it supports the formation of a Palestinian state in only 50% of the West Bank.

* Mufdal Party: In 1955, the Mufdal Party was formed from a coalition of the two Mizrahi parties and the Union of Religious Workers with a national-religious orientation. Mufdal has religious and nationalist orientations. The political party is known as a partner of the government.

* Shas Party: This party was founded in 1984 by a political rabbi named Arya Dori and is another religious party in Israel.

* Mortas Party: It was formed from the union of 3 smaller parties named Raz, Mapam and Shinoi. Mertz is a staunch supporter of religious freedom and emphasizes pluralism in Israeli society, and is therefore considered the opposite of Shas in Israeli society. (Shlomo Sand • 2019: 389)

* Kadima Party: This party was founded by Ariel Sharon.

* Arab Party: There are three Arab parties in Israel that send representatives to the Knesset in proportion to their pro-population population.

*Blue and White Party: A political alliance in Israel formed to compete in the Israeli general election. The alliance defines itself as a pluralistic and moderate political party that encompasses all sections of Israel's political and religious spectrum. The name of this alliance is derived from the colors of the Israeli flag. The leaders of this alliance are Bani Gantz and Yair Lapid, and they are accompanied by a group of Israeli political soldiers, including Moshe Ya'alon and Gabi Ashkenaz. In the Israeli general election in April 2019, he won 35 seats in the Knesset.

10. Formation of a government in Israel:

In February 2009, Israeli President Shimon Peres called on Benjamin Netanyahu to form a new Israeli government as Prime Minister. On April 1, 2009, Benjamin Netanyahu introduced his new cabinet to the Knesset and received 69 votes in favor. With 45 abstentions, 1 abstention and 5 abstentions, he won a vote of confidence for the new Israeli government, which includes 30 ministries. Benjamin Netanyahu's government has two women ministers and five Russian ministers. On April 5, 2009, the Israeli cabinet appointed Ozi Arad as chairman of the Supreme National Security Council of Israel at the suggestion of Benjamin Netanyahu.

Benjamin Netanyahu is currently the current Israeli Minister of the Knesset and the current leader of the Likud party, and is one of the most powerful figures in Israeli politics. Although the president of Israel is the head of state, his position is largely ceremonial, with the prime minister in charge. The prime minister's official residence is in Jerusalem. Benjamin Netanyahu is the ninth prime minister of the regime, excluding the caretaker government. Netanyahu resigned from his post at the Israeli Ministry of Finance in August 2005 in protest of a plan to oust Israeli settlers from Gaza, ousted Ariel Sharon, and re-elected to the Likud party in August 2006.

11- Israel's foreign policy:

Israel is an official member of the United Nations and has diplomatic allies in many countries around the world. Currently, more than one hundred and sixty countries in the world recognize Israel and have full diplomatic relations with that country. All Western countries, parts of South America, Asia and Africa have also recognized Israel.

The Carnegie Endowment for International Peace in Moscow has published an analytical article examining the limits and requirements of the Zionist regime's foreign policy. The Israeli regime's foreign policy is often mistakenly reduced to its geopolitical sphere. Although Tel Aviv's vital interests are concentrated in the Middle East, its economic, political, and lobbying resources can make it a regional power with global reach. In its analysis, the Carnegie Endowment for International Peace has identified the school of realism as the dominant ideological tradition of the Israeli regime. Thus, and based on this school, the foreign policy of this regime is based on the three principles of survival in an environment full of conflict, the pursuit of power and the formation of coalitions. The regime's foreign policy is also deeply linked to its long-standing traditions. (Rah Peyk, 1999 255)

12- The Zionist regime and the issue of Palestine

After 70 years of the occupation of Palestine by the Zionist regime, there are two important approaches to this occupation:

Resistance approach and compromise approach: Resistance approach and denial of the nature of the Zionist regime was formed after the Islamic Revolution of Iran and under the leadership of Imam Khomeini (PBUH). During the resistance, in addition to Iran, Syria, Lebanon's Hezbollah, Hamas and "Islamic Jihad" (inside the occupied territories) are present. The Gaza Strip is now under Hamas control. Representatives of the Reconciliation Movement are the Palestine Liberation Organization, the Fatah Organization, and the Palestinian Authority, led by Mahmoud Abbas. The organization was established after the signing of the Oslo Accords in

1994 as the Arab representative in the negotiations, and now controls the West Bank. The late Yasser Arafat, after years of guerrilla struggle against the Israeli occupation, formed the Fatah Organization and the Palestine Liberation Organization, and was eventually assassinated in 2004 by the same regime.

13. Israel's wars in the Middle East:

1. The Arab-Israeli War of 1948: A war that the Israelis call the "War of Independence" or the "War of Liberation." The Palestinians often refer to this war and the ensuing battles as "misery." This war marked the beginning of the Arab-Israeli animosity that continues to this day.

2. The Suez Canal War (1956): The Suez Crisis was the occupation of Egypt in late 1956 by Israel, followed by France and Britain. Its goals were to regain control of the Suez Canal and oust Egyptian President Gamal Abdel Nasser. After the start of the war, the United States, the Soviet Union and the United Nations forced the three occupying countries to withdraw. This incident humiliated Great Britain and France and strengthened Nasser.

3- The Six-Day War (1967): This war took place from June 5 to June 10, 1967 between Israel and the Arab countries of Egypt, Syria and Jordan, and ended with the absolute victory of Israel, leading to the occupation of parts of the lands of the three Arab countries by Israel. The battle began with a sudden Israeli airstrike on Egyptian air bases, and within six days the country managed to take the Gaza Strip and the Sinai Desert out of Egypt's control and annex it, as well as control east of Jerusalem and the West Bank. Jordan withdrew and annexed the Golan Heights from Syrian control and annexed its territory, tripling Israel's size. One million Arabs came under Israeli rule after this war.

4. The Yom Kippur War (1973): On the evening of October 6, 1973, on the eve of Yom Kippur (which is sacred to the Jews and is celebrated by fasting), the Syrian and Egyptian armies launch a surprise attack on Israel. They started. The war lasted until October 25. At first, Egyptian forces advanced into Sinai, but three days later, Israel repulsed the attack with a large-scale offensive. Syria, which had a lightning strike, also faced resistance and defense from the Israeli army and was forced to retreat. Israel was able to recapture the Golan Heights, and finally, with the defeat of the Egyptian, Jordanian and Syrian forces, the Arabs were disgraced and humiliated.

The hostility between Egypt and Israel ended with the signing of the Camp David Peace Treaty in 1978, and Israel returned Sinai to Egypt, and Egypt formally recognized Israel as an independent state.

The hostility between Jordan and Israel ended in 1994 with the signing of the Madrid Peace Treaty mediated by US President Bill Clinton. The Syrian-Israeli peace talks have not yet yielded results.

5. Lebanon Civil War (1982): It was a multifaceted civil war that lasted from 1975 to 1990 and left about 120,000 people dead. By 2012, approximately 76,000 people were still displaced. As a result of this war, one million people also left Lebanon. One of these internal conflicts was the conflict in southern Lebanon, which resulted in the defeat of the free Lebanese government with Israeli support (1979-1983) and its replacement by the Israeli security zone (occupied areas of southern Lebanon).

6. The Israel-Lebanon War (2006): The Israel-Lebanon War, known in Israel as the Second Lebanon War and in Lebanon as the July War, is a 33- or 34-day war between the Israeli army and Hezbollah in Lebanon. It took place and spread to the north of Israel and all over Lebanon.

7. The Battle of Israel and Gaza 2008-2009: The battle of Israel and Hamas in Gaza is part of the Arab-Israeli conflict that lasted from December 27, 2008 to January 17, 2009. In Israel, the operational name is Operation Molten Lead, and among the Arabs it is referred to as the Ghaha Massacre. As the first day of the battle, with the largest number of Palestinians killed and wounded, ended in one day since 1948, this day became known to some Arabs as Black Saturday. The result of this war was the end of a six-month ceasefire between Israel and Hamas.

8. Scattered conflicts with Syria, Lebanon and the Palestinians (2009 to date): Israel is currently engaged in conflicts with the Palestinians in their territories. The territories that have been occupied by Israel since the 1967 Six-Day War are in dispute despite the signing of the Oslo Accords on September 13, 1993. (Jafari, 144: 2004)

The Palestinians want the Gaza Strip and the West Bank, located west and east of Israel, respectively, to become an independent (and preferably interconnected) state under a UN partition plan. Negotiations, threats and repeated wars between Israel and Syria and Lebanon to reach a point of stability have not yet been concluded. (Akins, 100: 1999)

14- Regional arrangements:

One of the long-standing traditions of the regime is the "alliance with the periphery", which was formed in the 1950s. The Coalition Doctrine was formed based on the development of close ties with non-Arab Muslim countries in the Middle East. At that time, Turkey and Iran were the targets of this doctrine before the revolution. Over time, that is likely to change. Turkey's behavior is currently interpreted as unfriendly to Israel, and Iran is seen as a serious threat. In addition, with the rise of ISIS, the situation of the Israeli regime in the region has become increasingly challenged. It seems that in the current situation, the doctrine of periphery, which was long out of the agenda, has been reconsidered. With the exception that this time, the purpose of this doctrine is an area. The target region is the Caucasus. Tel Aviv's presence in the Caucasus increased during the first decade of the twentieth century with the establishment of various departments and departments by the Israeli regime in various Central Asian and Caucasus countries, which after the war in South Ossetia in 2008, Tel Aviv to avoid conflict with Moscow reduced its activities in Georgia. In contrast, Azerbaijan attracted the attention of the Israeli regime as a new option. It is noteworthy that the Israeli regime sees Azerbaijan as a key to controlling Iran in the Middle East. Tehran and Baku disagree on four main issues:

1- The situation in the Caspian Sea

2- The issue of Nagorno-Karabakh, in which Iran supported the position of Armenia, and finally Azerbaijan won.

3- Azerbaijan in Iran, where about twenty million Azeri people live.

4- Factor Religious: Azerbaijan condemns Iran for inciting religious sentiments in the Shiite but secular country of Azerbaijan. (Iranian diplomacy site, 08/03/2015)

15- Looking at the Arabic field; Israel has a new regional policy:

It seems that as Israel continues to try to establish relations with Arab countries, the conditions will be created for the spread of Iranophobia. Israel, which has been at war with the Arab world since 1948, intends to end the situation in order to achieve its goals of Iranophobia. This is a clear turn in Israeli foreign policy. In 2017, Israeli officials met with a retired Saudi army general at the King David Hotel, a meeting unprecedented since 1948. The policy change was seen in other Arab countries as well, with the Israeli Energy Minister meeting with a UAE official in January and the two sides agreeing to establish an Israeli business center in Abu Dhabi. The change in policy stems from the emergence of strategic and important issues for these countries and Israel, including security, energy and participation in natural resources, although many of these issues occur behind the scenes. Recently, the then Israeli Minister of War stated in an interview with the Arab media that "Israel tends to share its information in various fields, including the exchange of security information to confront Iran with moderate Arab countries" (Samira Zarghami Khosravi et al., 2020: 16)

16- The Zionist regime and Iran:

The reason for Israel's enmity with Iran: After the victory of the Islamic Revolution, Iran changed from an ally of the West to an independent country with an ideology rooted in Islam. This caused the Islamic Republic of Iran to confront the ideology of Zionism and the occupying regime by recognizing the real threats. Despite all obstacles, Iran was able to revive its regional role and confront Israel by forming an all-inclusive coalition of Syria and the Lebanese Party, Islamic Jihad and Hamas in West Asia. This axis, with the continuation of the resistance, provided the ground for the liberation of southern Lebanon in 2000 and the Gaza Strip in 2005, and will continue to confront the Zionist regime. The actions of the resistance axis have caused the decline of the Zionist regime and today Iran has become the biggest enemy and threat to the existence of Israel.

In contrast, Benjamin Netanyahu is a staunch opponent of Iran's acquisition of a nuclear weapon, calling it the most important threat to Israel's existence and security. Following the popular protests of the reformists against the results announced in the tenth round of the Iranian presidential election, Netanyahu in an emotional action praised the supporters of the opposition in Iran and stated that the brave people of Iran have shown the true face of Iran. Netanyahu also compared Iran to Nazi Germany in the US Congress and strongly opposed Iran's efforts to achieve uranium enrichment. In December 2020, Iran's nuclear scientist and Deputy Defense Minister, Dr. Mohsen Fakhrizadeh, was assassinated by the Israeli intelligence service (Mossad), and the regime welcomed the assassination, despite not taking responsibility. Iran also blamed Israel for the assassination of its nuclear scientist. (IRNA news website 28/11/2020)

Sardar Hossein Alaei, the first commander of the IRGC navy and a professor at Imam Hussein University, also announced in a message on the occasion of the martyrdom of Dehkrat Fakhrizadeh that the number of martyrs of Iran's nuclear scientist was seven, all of whom were martyred by Mossad. (Entekhab Site. 29/11/2020)

17- The issue of assassination and citation of Mossad to Talmud:

The Israeli intelligence service is called Mossad, which operates under the auspices of the Israeli Prime Minister. One of the main features of Mossad in recent years is the issue of assassinating Iranian nuclear scientists and Israeli rivals in the region. Israeli Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu has stressed that Israel's intelligence services must use both old and new methods to "target assassination" at the same time.

If they ask Israeli intelligence agents, officials or legislators, what is their justification for the policy of targeted killing and all this assassination? Most of them mention this "stand up and take the initiative in killing him" as its religious and moral justification. The Zionists carried out targeted killings even before the establishment of Israel. For example, the two Zionist militant groups, the Irgon Group and the Lahi, led by Menachem Begin, used targeted killings to accelerate the process of ending British rule in Palestine. But the fateful decision to turn targeted killings into official and secret Israeli policy was made by David Ben-Gurion, Israel's first prime minister. (Saadat, 139: 17)

It is estimated that by 2018, Israel has carried out 2,700 "targeted killings". Assassination of nuclear scientists is one of Israel's tactics to maintain nuclear supremacy in the Middle East and monopolize nuclear weapons. This tactic intensified with the assassination of Egyptian nuclear scientists in the 1970s, and in the 1980s and 1990s, Iraqi nuclear scientists were targeted one after another. Even French and Canadian scientists collaborating with Iraq did not escape the reach of Mossad agents. The wave of targeted assassinations of Mossad has reached Iran in the last decade (1980s and 1990s). Recently, following the Israeli regime's assassination of scientists, the assassination of Dr. Mohsen Fakhrizadeh on Friday, December 28, 1999, as experts have stated the assassination was carried out by Ayadi and the mercenaries of the Israeli intelligence service, which, of course, could have been carried out with the help of other intelligence services in line with Tel Aviv. (Samira Zarghami Khosravi and others, 2020: 17)

Foreign Policy of the Islamic Republic: The foreign policy of the Islamic Republic of Iran is based on several principles that guide the behavior and action of foreign policy in the international arena. According to official documents, especially the constitution, Imam Khomeini's statements and the behavioral performance of the various governments of the Islamic Republic, especially after the fall of Bani Sadr, it can be said that the principles of the foreign policy of the Islamic Republic are: "Denial of domination", "Arrogance", "Oppression", "Justice", "Support for the oppressed and deprived", "Support and defense of the rights of Muslims", "Peaceful coexistence and peace", "Non-interference in the internal affairs of countries and "Mutual respect", "Commitment to treaties, treaties and international law" and the like. (Ghanbarloo, 174: 2008)

In fact, "Supporting and defending the rights of Muslims implicitly addresses countries that are building oppression against Muslims, which is clearly seen in the views of the Islamic Republic of Iran against the Israeli government and its occupation." . Support for the oppressed and liberation movements also clearly states that Israel is the main enemy of the Islamic Republic of Iran "(Samira Zarghami Khosravi et al., 2016: 9)

The definition of Israel as an adversary has led to Israel trying to find a way to maximize its national security, and Iranophobia is part of this long-term project in the region and the world. (Samira Zarghami Khosravi and others, 2020: 9)

However, "It seems that the nature of Iran's foreign policy after the revolution and the reason for the various decisions taken by the country's officials can be the importance of the issue of independence and maintaining the Islamic Republic in a political geopolitics" (Samira Zarghami Khosravi et al., 2020: 9).

The main factors that have contributed to the spread of Iranophobia from Israel's point of view are divided into several sections:

1- Factors of nature which are divided into two parts:

a: The approach of oppression and protection of the oppressed and Muslim rights in the foreign policy of the Government of the Islamic Republic of Iran, which has been mentioned above.

b: Iran's geopolitics (Israel's fear of Iran's growing power in the region due to its power components such as land size, access to open waters, etc.);

2 - Tactical factors that include: a) nuclear activities of the Islamic Republic of Iran

b) The signing of the nuclear deal agreement between the Islamic Republic of Iran and the P5 + 1, A situation that greatly angered Israel and efforts to spread Iranophobia. Of course, Israel's opposition and hostility to nuclear deal has been repeated from the time the nuclear talks became public until Benjamin Netanyahu accepted nuclear deal.

3. Strategic factors;

a) The support of the Islamic Republic of Iran to the Islamic Jihad, Hamas and Hezbollah in Lebanon

b) The expansion of Iran's strategic depth to the borders of Israel with the presence of Iranian forces in Syria since the rise of ISIS until now (Akins, 1987: 31)

Conclusion:

Israel has set its foreign policy against Iran and seeks to undermine Iran's position in the Middle East by raising the issue of Iranophobia. Israel is trying to spread Iranophobia by addressing issues such as the nuclear issue, opposition to the IAEA, the Islamic Republic of Iran's support for Islamic resistance groups such as Hamas, Islamic Jihad and Hezbollah in Lebanon, as well as the presence of Iranian forces in Syria from a security perspective. Tel Aviv, on the other hand, was using US aid under Donald Trump to seek Arab cooperation to form and legitimize a Hebrew, Arab, and Western coalition against the Islamic Republic of Iran. Impose a lot of pressure on Iran. Numerous accusations against Iran over the explosion of Aramco's oil facilities (August 17, 1998) prove this. At present, Israel is trying to distort the Iranian authorities by using false slogans about the peaceful nuclear activities of the Islamic Republic of Iran. In fact, what worries Israel is not Iran's nuclear strategy, but the influence of the Islamic Republic of Iran in the region, which has caused fear in Israel. It is explicitly mentioned in Israel's 2020 National Security Document. (Dehshiri, 258: 2001)

In the political arena, Netanyahu is a staunch opponent of Iran in acquiring a nuclear weapon and considers it the most important threat to Israel's existence and security. Israel should be considered one of the most ideological countries in the world. The Israeli racism debate is also inspired by the ideology of the Jewish people. Ideology is so entwined in Israel's political structure that it renders it unconstitutional. Israel has no constitution, and operates a set of laws that are superior to public law, called the constitution, instead of the constitution. The first law of Israel is the Torah. (Reza Saadat, p. 216: 2012)

Ideologically, the Israeli authorities, referring to parts of the jurisprudential interpretation of the Torah (Talmud), believe that: "If someone comes to kill you, stand up and kill him!" Based on this, they have committed many hostile acts, including the assassination of Iraqi and Iranian nuclear scientists, as well as the assassination of Hamas leaders on Netanyahu's orders in the Middle East. Israel considers itself the superior nation that will rule the world. With these interpretations, if in terms of political structure, another dominant

party rules over Israel that does not have extremist nationalist ideas, it is still because of the ideology of Israeli ethnic superiority and the usurpation of Muslim lands in Palestine by this regime with the ideology and political structure of Iran, Iraq, the axis of resistance and other Muslim countries are in conflict, but now Israel, relying on the tradition of alliance with the periphery, by establishing peace and normalization of relations with Muslim countries including the UAE and Bahrain and the presence in the Caucasus region and trying equations Shake the Middle East to challenge regional powers such as Iran, Russia and Turkey. These three dimensions will naturally respond to any new power in the region. And these reactions will cause tension and insecurity in the region, especially in Iran.

Provide a solution: Iran should further expand its diplomatic relations in the region, especially with Muslim countries, and should not rely on a military factor as a deterrent. The success of diplomacy depends on rules, including diplomacy, which must be free of the belligerent spirit of recent mistakes by Iran, the severance of diplomatic relations with the Muslim country of Saudi Arabia, and the coldening of relations with Azerbaijan. After the independence of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the Islamic Republic of Iran, due to ethnicity and concerns about the strengthening of Turkish nationalism in the north and west of Iran, reduced the expansion of relations with Azerbaijan, which led to Azerbaijan's inclination towards Israel, which indicated Iran's poor performance in the northern neighbor. The same is true in the case of Saudi Arabia and the UAE, despite deep-rooted religious differences, and reducing conflicts and increasing commonalities (religious, human) can be a way out and reduce Israel's rise to power and the growing number of Israeli supporters and allies in the region.

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